

ISOLATION AND IDENTIFICATION OF MICROORGANISMS FROM SURFACES IN SCIENCE LABORATORIES

^{a*}Isola O.B ^bOlatunji E.O

^a Department of Chemical Sciences, ^b Department of Biological Sciences,
Samuel Adegboyega University Ogwa, Edo State, Nigeria

*E-mail: bamijos4all@yahoo.com Tel:+23434553580, +2347064644527,

ABSTRACT

The microorganisms that are associated with laboratory surfaces were characterized and identified. Swabs of surfaces from four different laboratories (Physics, Chemistry, Biology and Microbiology) were aseptically taken. The swabs were streaked on macConkey, chocolate and sabouraud agar respectively and appropriately incubated. Distinct colonies were randomly selected and characterized phenotypically. Morphological features were examined and biochemical tests carried out include; Gram staining, coagulase, catalase, urease, and sugar fermentation test. Microorganisms identified were *Bacillus cereus* with percentage occurrence of 30.77%, *Bacillus subtilis* with percentage occurrence of 30.77%, *Bacillus alvei* with percentage occurrence of 7.692%, *Bacillus macerans* with percentage occurrence of 15.384%, *Staphylococcus aureus* with percentage occurrence of 7.692%, and *Salmonella* species with percentage occurrence of 7.692%. No growth was observed on the sabouraud agar which indicates that the specimens were completely free from fungi.

Keywords: Isolation and identification, surface microorganism, science laboratories.

INTRODUCTION

Microorganisms are known to be ubiquitous. They are found in different parts of the terrestrial environment including various surfaces. Natural environment such as air, water, soil and animal fluid are agents of microorganism. Many people can become infected from the air especially those microorganisms causing respiratory-tract infection, other means of acquisition of microorganisms are food and food products, suspended solid materials source including dust, dry soil and droplets or moisture from coughing, sneezing or talking and also from growth of sporulating mould on walls and floor (Winslour, 1996). Hence nearly all microorganisms may be found in air but most especially those kinds which are more resistance to dryness will survive for a longer period. Not only air but soil contains the greatest variety of microorganisms that readily contaminate the body surfaces of animals and plants. Cappuccino and Sherman, 2002, showed that the most important ones are various moulds, yeast and some species of bacteria such as species of *Bacillus*, *Micrococcus*, and *Escherichia*. In addition, water contains not only the natural floral but also microorganisms from soil and animal, chiefly species of *Pseudomonas*, *Bacillus*, *Micrococcus*, *Proteus*, *Enterobacteria*, *Chromobacteria* and *Escherichia*.

Costerton et al; 1978 put forth a theory of biofilms that explained the mechanisms whereby microorganisms adhere to living and nonliving materials and the benefits accrued by this ecologic niche. Biofilms may form on a wide variety of surfaces, including living tissues, indwelling medical devices, industrial or potable water system piping, or natural aquatic systems. Transport of microorganisms to surfaces and subsequent attachment are governed mainly by physical forces. In the water phase microbes are transported by gravity, currents, turbulence, Brownian motion, and motility. Micro-turbulence, Brownian motion, diffusion, and motility are the dominating forces for transportation within the viscous layer (a physically well-structured water film which covers solid surfaces in water) (Lutz-Arend Meyer-Reil, 1994). Other characteristics of the aqueous medium, such as pH, nutrient levels, ionic strength, and temperature, may play a role in the rate of microbial attachment to a substratum. Several studies have shown a seasonal effect on bacterial attachment and biofilm formation in different aqueous systems (Donlan et al., 1994). Once attached to surfaces, bacteria start to divide. Within a short period of time, heterogeneous assemblages of organisms (biofilms) originate which - together with the spectrum of particles - cause the complex structure of natural sediments (Rodney M. Donlan, 2002). Microorganisms commonly associated with biofilms on indwelling medical devices include: *Staphylococcus aureus*, Coagulase-negative staphylococci, *Enterococcus* spp, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and *Klebsiella pneumoniae*. Characteristics of biofilms that can be important in infectious disease processes include, the detachment of cells or biofilm aggregates may result in bloodstream or urinary tract infections or in the production of emboli, cells may exchange resistance plasmids within biofilms, cells in biofilms have dramatically reduced susceptibility to antimicrobial agents, biofilm-associated gram-negative bacteria may produce endotoxins, and biofilms are resistant to host immune system clearance.

Source of infection- The term source of infection refers to the normal growth habitat of the microbe e.g. a site in the body of the human or animal host. Objects contaminated with live but temporarily inactive microbes may act as vehicles or reservoirs of infection agents and not sources of infection. Human diseases may be acquired by the mechanisms of exogenous infection that is from outside sources such as school laboratory (windows, sinks, benches, and door), from human patients with clinical infections (Nosocomial), healthy human carriers of the pathogenic microorganisms and also from formites in the laboratory. On the other hand, Endogenous infection refers to sources of a clinical infection within the patient's own body (Smith and Pearce, 1986). For instance *Pseudomonas* and *Bacillus* species are of particular importance in a hospital setting, where they are common cause of infection.

Routes of transmission- This refers to the mechanism by which an infection and non-infection agent is transferred from one person to the other or from the reservoir to a new host. This may occur by contact through person to person, or indirectly through contaminated object (formites). Transmission of infections are more likely to occur where there is overcrowding, movement of people in that direction, low sunshine and also tend to be more marked in urban areas such as school than in a rural area where we have less population. As reported by (F.J Baker et al.,

2002), Some highly contagious infection spread through casual contact, the type of contact which occurs in day to day activities at home, work or school. Laboratory workers occasionally become infected from artificial cultures or from infected diagnostic materials collected from experimental animals.

This study therefore aims at revealing the profile of bacteria associated with surfaces in Science laboratories in Federal Polytechnic, Ede.

MATERIALS AND METHOD

MATERIALS

Sample collection

A total number of 32 Swab Samples were obtained from surfaces of work benches, sinks, windows, and doors in the four laboratories using sterile cotton swab sticks. Each swab samples were collected in duplicates from the surfaces.

Fig. 1 Flow chart of experimental procedure

Preparation of media and sterilization

Three solids agar were used in the course of this experimental work. These were sabouraud dextrose agar (Oxoid), macConkey agar (Oxoid), and chocolate agar. Media were prepared and sterilized according to the manufacturer's instructions under proper aseptic conditions.

Isolation and identification

Swab Samples taken from surfaces of work benches, sinks, windows, and doors in the four laboratories were inoculated on the microbes-free-melted agar plates the very day the samples were collected and cultivated sterile plate of sabouraud agar, macConkey agar, and chocolate agar. The plate were then covered and incubated at 37°C for 24 hours to 48 hours. The purity plates were stored in the refrigerator. The microbes were identified by Gram's staining,

differential and selective media, and appropriate conventional biochemical tests (Cowon and Steel, 1993).

RESULTS

Table 1: Biochemical characteristics of bacterial isolates from different laboratoriesurfaces

Name of Laboratory	Isolates code	Cell shape	Gram reaction	Motility	Catalase	Coagulase	Citrate	Urease	Indole	Sugar fermentation			Probable identity
										Glucose	Xylose	Arabinose	
Physics Lab.	A1	GPB	+	+	NA	NA	-	-	-	+	-	-	<i>B. cereus</i>
	A2	GPB	+	+	NA	NA	-	-	-	+	+	+	<i>B. subtilis</i>
	A3	GPB	+	+	NA	NA	-	-	+	+	-	-	<i>B. alvei</i>
	A4	GPC	+	NA	+	+	NA	NA	NA	+	NA	NA	<i>S. aureus</i>
Chemistry Lab.	B1	GPB	+	+	NA	NA	-	-	-	+	+	+	<i>B. subtilis</i>
	B2	GNB	-	+	NA	NA	+	-	-	+	-	+	<i>S. typhae</i>
	B3	GPB	+	+	NA	NA	-	-	-	+	-	-	<i>B. cereus</i>
Biology Lab.	C1	GPB	+	+	NA	NA	-	-	-	+	-	-	<i>B. cereus</i>
	C2	GPB	+	+	NA	NA	-	-	-	+	+	+	<i>B. subtilis</i>
	C3	GPB	+	+	NA	NA	-	-	-	+	+	-	<i>B. macerans</i>
Microbiology Lab.	D1	GPB	+	+	NA	NA	-	-	-	+	+	-	<i>B. macerans</i>
	D2	GPB	+	+	NA	NA	-	-	-	+	+	+	<i>B. subtilis</i>
	D3	GPB	+	+	NA	NA	-	-	-	+	-	-	<i>B. cereus</i>

NA: Not Applicable

DISCUSSION

The result shows that the commonest microorganism or bacteria from laboratory surfaces are species of *Bacilli* e.g. *Bacillus cereus*; *Bacillus subtilis*; *Bacillus alvei*; and *Bacillus macerans*. Others include *Salmonella typhae* and *Styphylococcus aureus*. Among these species, *B. cereus* and *B. subtilis* have the highest percentage of occurrences (30.77%) followed by *B. macerans* with percentage occurrence of (15.384%) and *B. alvei*, *Salmonella typhae* and *S. aureus* have percentage occurrence of (7.692%). Majority of the organisms isolated are members of genus *Bacilli* which are large gram positives rod characterized by their ability to produce heat resistance endospores. The genus is a very large one comprising of both strict aerobes and facultative anaerobes bacteria. *Bacilli* are widely distributed in nature and are found in large numbers in moist soil and water samples and many of their most distinctive features are attributed to the quest for native habitat (Jason et al, 1994). At present, species of *Bacillus* are encountered primarily in clinical microbiology laboratory as contaminants or as reagent for testing the effectiveness of methods of sterilization (Joklik et al., 1981).

Figure 2: Percentage occurrence of bacteria isolated from different laboratories surfaces

Bacillus cereus an aerobic spore forming bacilli is an infrequently recognized cause of food borne illness in the United State (Bergeys, 1978). It is similar to *Bacillus anthrax* in cellular morphology, but unlike *B. anthrax* it is usually motile, β -hemolytic and is not susceptible to gammaphage. *B. cereus* food poisoning can cause two clinical syndromes. The first has a short incubation period of 4 hours. It is characterized clinically by severe nausea and vomiting and is frequently mistaken for staphylococcus food poisoning. Epidemic has been described following the injection of such foods as fried rice in which extensive multiplication of the organisms had occurred. The second syndrome has a longer incubation periods (17 hour) and is characterized by abdominal cramping and diarrhea. It is commonly confused with clostridia food poisoning. The basics mechanism of *B. cereus* food poisoning relates to the facts that the spore forms survive cooking and that the food is allowed to reach the temperature that permit germination of the spore and elaboration of the enterotoxin. Strains of *B. cereus* elaborate at least two enterotoxins that act differently in experimental animals depending on the nature of the outbreak from which the strains were initially isolated. Proof of the cause of *B. cereus* food poisoning usually depends upon the isolation of the same types of organism from the food and stools of infected patient. In addition to food poisoning, *B. cereus* has also been in serious infection associated with impairment of host defense mechanism primarily by foreign bodies, prosthetic devices, or restricted blood supply.

Bacillus subtilis is another species that can be found in air, dust brackish water and infusion of vegetable matter. It is usually common laboratory contaminant but *B. cereus*, is capable of producing infection in the compromised host. It has been seen in overwhelming bacteremia and eye infection which may produce serious endophthalmitis in heroin addicts and has been cultured from street heroin (Bergey, 1978). *B. subtilis* infection usually responds to therapy with the β -lactam antibiotics. Other species of the isolates are staphylococcus and salmonella species which are found as pathogens in man and animals.

Staphylococcus aureus is found as a commensal and pathogens of man and other animals and one major causes of food poisoning (staphylococcus enterotoxigenicosis), this is an intoxication caused by ingestion of an enterotoxin produced by *Staphylococcus aureus*. *S. aureus* is highly pathogenic and exists in air, water, dirt and excretions (Gui LI, et al., 2009). It is a common inhabitant of the nasal passages from which it is often contaminate the hands. It is also a frequent

cause of skin lesions on the hands which makes it very easy to get into food if allowed to incubate in the food. Staphylococcal food poisoning is characterized by nausea, vomiting and diarrhea 1-6 hours after its ingestion. *Staphylococcus aureus* produces several toxins that damage host tissue or increase the organism's virulence. Because the contamination of food cannot be avoided completely the most adequate method of preventing staphylococcus food poisoning is adequate refrigeration during storage to prevent toxin formation. In a nutshell, staphylococcus genus are gram positive cocci about 1 micro metre in diameter, they are often in clusters, some containing orange or yellow carotenoid pigment, non-motile, facultative anaerobic which is positive to catalase and coagulase biochemical test.

Salmonella genus (family enterobacteriaceae) is also found as pathogens in man and other animals. They cause bacterial infections, the disease which result from growth in body tissues rather than the ingestion of food and drink already contaminated by microbial growth compared with bacteria intoxication, bacterial infection such as salmonella usually have long incubation periods (from 12 hours to 22 weeks) needed from the organisms to grow in the tissue of the host by some fever indicative of the host response of infection. Salmonella bacteria are gram negative, facultative anaerobic, non-endospore forming, usually motile rods that ferment glucose to produce acid and gas, their normal habitats is the intestinal tracts of human and animals. Prevention of salmonellosis depends on good sanitation practice to the decontamination and on proper refrigeration to prevent increases in bacterial numbers.

CONCLUSION

The risk of exposure to a biological agent is very high in the laboratory, microorganism exists in the laboratory through many means such as air, animal, or human agents when talking, sneezing, and coughing in the laboratory. In microbiology laboratory it is advisable not to talk while culturing, pouring and isolation to prevent contamination by mouth microbes. Also there is a possibility of transferring microorganisms from one laboratory to the other during the course of activities that involves moving of materials and experimental animals. Control measures that are adequate for the routine circumstances of daily life might be used such as washing and scrubbing soaps and detergents to control undesirable microorganism and viruses to some extent. When working in the laboratory, all staff and students must wear protective clothing e.g. lab coat which should not be worn for more than two days and should be placed in receptacle prior to autoclaving. Protective clothing worn in the laboratory must be taken off before visiting test rooms, recreational rooms, canteens, library or other part of the premises. Washing hands in disinfectant before and after any experiment in the laboratory is very necessary, and sickness records and records of immunization, chest X-rays, and job associated injuries must be kept by a designated person.

REFERENCES

Adebesin A.A, Oladapo O.G, Bolaji A.S, Egbeyemi O.T, Lawal I.A, Awe F.A, Akinyele H.A, Raji A.A, Akande J.O, and Iromini F.A (2002): A biology Practical Guide for Science Laboratory Technology 40, 43-48.

Cappuccino and Sherman (2002): Microbiology Laboratory Manual, 4th Edition.

Costerton JW, Geesey GG, Cheng K-J (1978). How bacteria stick. *Sci Am.*; 238:86–95.

Cowan and Steel (1993): Manual of identification of medical bacteria Ed. Cowan. Cambridge University Press, pp. 317.

Donlan RM, Pipes WO, Yohe TL (1994). Biofilm formation on cast iron substrata in water distribution systems, *Water Res*; 28:1497–1503.

F.J Baker, R.E Silverton and C.J Pallister (1989); Introduction to Medical Laboratory Technology; pg. 6-8, 308-309.

Fera P, Siebel MA, Characklis WG, Prieur D (1989). Seasonal variations in bacterial colonization of stainless steel, aluminum, and polycarbonate surfaces in a seawater flow system. *Bio-fouling*; 1:251–61.

Gui LI, Ren LAI, Gang DUAN, Long-Bao LYU, Zhi-Ye ZHANG, Huang LIU, XunXIANG (2009): Isolation and identification of symbiotic bacteria from the skin, mouth, and rectum of wild and captive tree shrews, *journal of Zoological Research* 35 (6): 492–499.

Janson, Wright and Robinson (1994): bacilli in microbiology for health science; 273.

Joklik, Willet and Amos (1981): Zinser microbiology; 673.

Lutz-Arend Meyer-Reil (1994): Microbial life in sedimentary biofilms – the challenge to microbial ecologists, *journal of marine ecology progress series*, Vol. 112: 303-311.

Nester, Anderson, Robbert and Pearsall (3rd Edition): Human perspective of microbiology; 113-124.

Paul Singleton (4th Edition): Bacteria in microbiology, biotechnology and medicine; 375 and 376.

Rodney M. Donlan, 2002: Microbial Life on Surfaces, *journal of emerging infectious diseases*, vol. 8, number 9.

Wisbeishir (6th Edition): microbiology in practice; 7.

World Health Organization (2nd Edition): General Principles of Laboratory Biosafety Manual, Geneva, 1.

World Health Organization (2nd Edition): Malaria Research Microscopy, Learner's Guide Book 1.